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CDIO as the definitive tool for Engineering Curriculum Development

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ABSTRACT

In recent years engineering education and real-world demands by engineers are increasingly more disparate, there are many examples of upgrading that our engineers must follow before starting to work for a company.

This element is associated with the fact that many students of Technical Engineering, or STEM subjects in general, do not have a future vision of the job they want to opt for, simply because this job post has not yet been invented/developed. With the purpose of preparing the Engineering students in a closer and better way to the current working world and working market, more and more institutions and individuals follow the CDIO initiative [1].

The common result, in addition to the improvement in the passing rates, is the fulfillment of the required competences in the subject and the satisfaction of having

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been able to learn motivated, acquiring a personal security that will be reflected in their attitude in the world of work.

In this paper we show immediate practical elements to implement CDIO in the centers, but not only that, we go a little further and define a guide of guidelines so that the CDIO initiative can be an active element in the curricular development of Engineering degrees.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: Curriculum Development, CDIO, Engineering Education

INTRODUCTION

In order to prepare the engineering students for the improvement of techniques and tools that meet the needs of business and society, the development of a methodology for teaching CDIO (Conceiving — Designing — Implementing — Operating) is carried out in educational classrooms.

The students perform innovation and invention of new products and systems through the implementation of the knowledge and technical foundations.

CDIO also becomes an attraction for companies looking for people able to highlight the features of the engineer as results of these students.

From the CDWG of SEFI we think that the CDIO initiative is the definitive agent to improve the curriculum of our students in an effective way.

1 THE CDIO INITIATIVE

The CDIO™ INITIATIVE is an innovative educational framework for producing the next generation of engineers. The framework provides students with an education stressing engineering fundamentals set in the context of Conceiving — Designing — Implementing — Operating (CDIO) real-world systems and products. Since Boeing issued a list of “Desired Attributes of an Engineer” in the nineties, changing higher education in engineering has been the subject of an on-going discussion among industries and engineering universities in the US and Western Europe. [2]

The CDIO initiative was designed specifically as a model that can be adapted and adopted by any University School of engineering. CDIO is a model of open architecture, it is available to be adapted to the specific needs of the University engineering programs. The participating universities (“contributors”) regularly develop methodologies and material to share with others.

The objective of engineering education is to educate students who are “ready to engineer,” that is, broadly prepared with both pre-professional engineering skills and deep knowledge of the technical fundamentals. It is the task of engineering educators to continuously improve the quality of undergraduate engineering education in order to meet this objective.

We could show three premises which reflect the principal goals of this new methodology [3]:

- That the underlying need is best met by setting goals that stress the fundamentals, while at the same time making the process of conceiving-designing-implementing operating products, processes, and systems the context of engineering education.
- That the learning outcomes for students should be set through stakeholder involvement, and met by constructing a sequence of integrated learning experiences, some of which are experiential, that is, they expose students to the situations that engineers encounter in their profession.
- That proper construction of these integrated learning activities will cause the activities to have dual impact, facilitating student learning of critical personal and interpersonal skills, and product, process, and system building skills, while simultaneously enhancing the learning of the fundamentals [4].

2 OUR HYPOTHESIS

There are so many advances, the growth of active people in CDIO and the benefits obtained by the students who experience it, that makes us think that the inclusion of the CDIO initiative in the curricular development of engineering education would improve the efficiency in the integral formation of students. For this, we will show different examples and indicators of improvements.

3 PRACTICAL EXAMPLES

This guide includes practical elements for CDIO teaching in subjects such as robotics, signal processing, computer programming, or bioengineering.

We also include aspects that we think are determinant and that would have to be in all curricular development in engineering [5]. The work methodology consists of a study of both the applied subjects and the mentioned initiative, extracting those common beneficial elements in the teaching of any degree in Engineering, and raising these elements for inclusion in the correct curricular development.

3.1 Degree in Mechanical Engineering of the Chalmers University, Sweden

Internal Combustion Engines and Chalmers Formula Student are the examples of the Chalmers University of Technology as examples of CDIO courses [6].

The learning objectives for Internal Combustion Engines making use of CDIO are:

- Be able to use basic combustion terminology
- Be able to describe the combustion process inside a cylinder, and specially the difference between an SI and a CI engine.
- Use the knowledge about combustion properties to design a combustion chamber

On the other hand, Formula Student is the largest engineering competition in the world with the aim of creating better engineers by giving the students hands-on experience. Every competing team designs, manufactures and tests a vehicle with which they then compete against other teams in several different events – all of this takes place during less than one year. There are both dynamic events such as

endurance and acceleration, and static events where the cost of manufacturing and the business idea of the project are presented to the judges.

The yearlong project of building a competent race car, provides the students with immense knowledge, experience and aids in moving from being a student to an accomplished engineer of tomorrow.

3.2 Degree in Computer Engineering of the Univ. of Cádiz, Spain

Carrying out more practice and less theory is the main aim of the subjects “Design of embedded computers” and “Microrobotic applications” between the third and fourth year of the Degree in Computer Engineering of the University of Cádiz. The students learn how to use a 3D printer and two numerical control machines in order to develop the project they will have to deliver at the end of the corresponding subject.

Forming groups, students will be able to apply their knowledge joining all the concepts learnt until that moment and also the technical skills, and the importance of systems integration in designing and building products. *Fig. 1.*

Professor is not who leads or directs in the classroom, but students, who are educated to lead the creation, increasing their ability to solve problems by themselves. The image of the teacher is translated to an advisor, facilitating and supporting demand for students. *Fig. 2.*

Fig. 1. Students supervised by the professor printing a piece modeled in 3D.

Fig. 2. Students mechanising a methacrylate sheet in a CNC cutting machine

Fig. 3. Students printing in the machine of Printer Circuit Board the design of a prototype board.

The evaluation of the results showed that this methodology helps students to be motivated during the learning and favours the future relationship with companies

though what initially will be internships demonstrating the company a different student profile that will be able to boost its benefits and since its incorporation and quickly work productively in engineering teams. *Fig. 3*.

3.3 CDIO design of five Engineering Programs at UCSC, Chile

The UCSC (Universidad Católica de la Santísima Concepción) School of Engineering redesigned the Computer Science, Industrial Engineering, Civil Engineering, Logistics Engineering and Aquacultural Biotechnology Engineering programs using a CDIO-based approach. [7]

They presented the motivations behind this work, namely, the desire to update the curricula so as to incorporate novel teaching and learning methodologies, and to improve their performance indicators. Their curriculum design process started in 2008, and to date they have completed the Conceive and Design phases of the CDIO approach, with the Implementation phase.

The active learning pilot experiences proved to be a very effective way of achieving the technical learning outcomes, as well as the so-called soft skills heretofore found lacking in previous students. Also, they were shown to highly motivate students as they engaged them in their own learning process. Introducing real engineering problems and experiences in the classroom helped students understand the fundamentals and see the theory into practice.

In retrospect, even though the curriculum design process described presented many difficulties and challenges, the application of the CDIO approach proved to be effective, synergistic and also a great hands-on learning experience.

3.4 Degree in Industrial Electronics Engineering of the Univ. of Cádiz, Spain

Fifteen students were selected for participating on this study for the subject "Automatic systems in intelligent buildings", framed in the fourth year of the plan of the engineering degree in Industrial Electronics of the University of Cádiz. [8]

The study is part of the search for alternatives to the practical teaching in the field of the home automation that allows students the access and manipulation of a domotic installation in conditions of hyper-realism, *Fig. 4*, and enables work in operations of optimization of energy efficiency, safety and comfort. Practice sessions were designed and evaluated on the control of a virtual home simulated with the software HOME I/o using different technological alternatives.

Fig. 4. Illustration of one of the scenarios designed for a practical session: automation of the living room of the digital housing.

Fig. 5 y Fig.6: Students working in the automation and domotics lab in the resolution of the tasks during a work session

In terms of the assessment of this experience, the participants had a very positive attitude towards the serious game as a tool for learning home automation concepts, and was found that the game was an entertaining, easy-to-use and very useful tool. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. Participants who completed the objectives set out in the working sessions showed high values on the scale of improvement of the ego while higher values on the scale of self preservation were obtained on those participants who did not complete the proposed tasks. Students improved their esteem associating their efficiency to a winning team.

The results suggest that the game can be used as a strategy of instructive method and as a motivation tool to improve technical skills, which coincides with similar teaching strategies proposed. Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Results of the evaluation

4 SUMMARY

A lot of students like engineering by the conviction that engineers build things and nevertheless feel disappointed by the first years of traditional engineering education when they are taught theory and complain that engineering education discourages them with a demanding schedule of the theory with little reward. By using experiential learning techniques, CDIO offers students a chance to develop a sense of strengthening and self-efficacy critical to their perception of self-worth. [9]

Showing that the education leads to higher quality employment is another factor in motivating students. Industries would prefer to hire engineers from CDIO programs because they have received excellent training in how to apply their basic theoretical knowledge to the development of practical product- or process-related projects and they will be more likely to succeed.

This new methodology, CDIO, also allows students to develop skills such as engineering reasoning and problem solving making the transition between university study and work life easier and quicker.

The list below shows the different subjects for some Engineering degrees marking those where the inclusion of the CDIO initiative in their curricular development would be recommended.

Information Technology Engineering	Aerospatial Engineering
Databases Administration	Mathematics Ampliation
Servers Administration	Avionics and Navigational Aid Systems
Computer Networks Security and Administration	Materials Science and Engineering
Algorithm Analysis and Data Structures	Elasticity and Resistance of Materials
Computer Architectures	Electricity
Parallel and Distributed Computer Architectures	Electrical Engineering
Quality of Computing Systems	Aeronautic Structural Elements
Calculus	Aeronautical Structures
Hypermedia Systems Development	Graphic Expression and Assisted Design
Multimedia Systems Development	Introduction to Aerospace Engineering
Direction and Management of Software Projects	Aerospace Materials
Algorithm Design	Flight Mechanics (Aircrafts)
Embedded Computer Design	Digital Electronic
Computer Networks Design	Aerial Navigation
Software Systems Design	
Principles of Computer Structures	Industrial Engineering
Principles of Physical and Electronic Computers	Electrical Activation
Implementation and Implantation of Software Systems	Elevation, Transport and Manutention Artifacts
Software Engineering	Microrobotics Automation
Web Engineering	Industrial Automation
Artificial Intelligence	Science and Engineering of Materials
Network Interconnections	Industrial Drawing
Internet and Electronic Business	Substations and Design of Transformation Centers
Programming Introduction	Configurable Electronic Design
Enterprise's Organization and Management	Graphic Expression and Assistive Design
Perception	Electrical Facilities
Language Processors	Industrial Facilities
Concurrent, Real-Time Programming	Electronic Instrumentation
Internet Programming	Lines and Electrical Networks
Object Oriented Programming	Industrial Maintenance
Parallel and Distributed Programming	Electrical Industrial Maintenance
Web Programming	Mechanisms and Machines
Informatics Projects	Fluid Mechanics
Pattern Recognition	Robot Mechanics
Information Recovery	Industrial Electrical Measurements
Computer Networks	Electric Machines
Security in Computer Systems	Chemistry
Enterprise Information Systems	Automatic Regulation
Distributed Systems	Microcontroller-based Automation Systems
Intelligent Systems	Smart Buildings Automatic Systems
Operative Systems	Power Electric System
Database Advanced Technologies	Environmental Technology
Computer Design Techniques	Fabrication Technology
Industrial Design and Product Development	Master in Industrial Engineering
Science and Engineering of Materials	Installations and Hydraulic / Thermic Machines
Technical Product Drawing	Electrical Technology
Assisted Computer Design	Machine Technology
Communication Design	Fabrication Integrated Systems
Electronic and Product Automation	Numeric Methods
Statistics	Electronic Design
Graphical Expression and Assistive Design	Quality Management
Graphic Product Engineering	Electronic Design
Material Resistance	

5 CONCLUSION

CDIO mode constructs the curriculum system according to the engineering concept, it trains technical experts and system engineers under the modern management mode and operation of the market mechanism [10]. The training objectives of the CDIO involve the role and the social responsibility of the engineers understanding the influence of the engineering to environment and society.

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